

Intro and informed consent

Welcome! This research is organised by the European Food Information Council (EUFIC) (Belgium). The purpose is to understand how nutrition professionals in Spain [Portugal] feel about plant-based dairy alternatives (PBDAs) (e.g., oat milk, soy yogurt). Results of this research may be published in a peer-reviewed journal.

Participation in this research is voluntary, and participants may cease their participation at any point without giving a reason. This survey will take about 10 minutes to fill in. The funding for this study comes from Alpro Iberia, but the study is conducted by EUFIC independently. If you have any questions, you may address them by email laura.fernandez@eufic.org [elisangela.rosario@eufic.org] or call +32 478 689 966 [+31 622 065 806].

By clicking on the box below, you give your consent to participate in this research and you acknowledge the following:

- I have read and understood the information above and have been given a full explanation of my role as participant and the likely duration of this research.
 - I understand that the information I provide will only be used for the purpose of this research.
 - I understand that all data relating to my participation in this research is held and processed in compliance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR).
 - I understand that all my responses will be anonymised.
 - The data from this research will be stored securely on the EUFIC server in Belgium for 5 years. Only authorised individuals within the organisation will be able to access the anonymised data.
 - I understand that my participation in this research is voluntary, and I am free to withdraw at any time without the need to justify my decision.
- I confirm that I have read and understood the above information and voluntarily agree to take part in this research. I have read and accept the [privacy statement \[privacy statement\]](#) regarding the processing of my personal data in the context of this research.
- I do not give my consent to participate in this research. [\[disqualified\]](#)

Profile

Q1a. What is your profession?

- Dietitian - nutritionist
- Student in nutrition (4th year degree or masters)
- Other

Q1b. What is your profession? [show only if Other is selected in Q1a]

- Researcher / academic in nutrition
- Other health professional
- Other [disqualified]

Q2. How many years of professional experience do you have?

Q3. Do you work directly with patients/clients? [do not show if Student in nutrition (4th year degree or masters) is selected in Q1a]

- Yes
- No

Awareness / Familiarity

Plant-based dairy alternatives (PBDAs) are made of plant-based ingredients like legumes (including soy), nuts, seeds, oats, rice, or coconut. They can take the form of alternatives to milk and yogurt. Some examples of PBDA are shown in the icons below.

Q4. How familiar are you with PBDAs?

- Not at all familiar
- Not so familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Q5. How frequently do you come across PBDAs when shopping for groceries in Spain [Portugal]?

- Never
- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Frequently
- Always

Use in professional practice

Q6. Among the micronutrients shown below, which three do you think the Spanish [Portuguese] population is most deficient in? Select three responses.

- Calcium
- Iodine
- Iron
- Magnesium
- Manganese
- Phosphorus
- Potassium
- Selenium
- Zinc
- Vitamin A
- Vitamin B1 (thiamine)
- Vitamin B2 (riboflavin)
- Vitamin B3 (niacin)
- Vitamin B9 (folate)
- Vitamin B12
- Vitamin C
- Vitamin D
- Vitamin E
- Vitamin K

Q7. How frequently do you recommend PBDAs to your patients/clients? [show only if they select Yes in Q3]

- Never
- To almost no patient/client (<10% of patients/clients)
- Few patients/clients (10-30% of patients/clients)
- A large portion of my patients/clients (31-70% of the patients/clients)
- Most of my patients/clients (>70% of the patients/clients)
- The entirety of my patients/clients (100% of the patients/clients)

Q7 adapted. Would you recommend PBDAs to consumers? [show only if they select No in Q3]

- Yes
- No

Q8. For what purpose(s) would you recommend PBDAs? Choose all that apply.

- Lactose intolerance & dairy allergies
- Food variety & dietary diversity
- Texture or taste preferences
- Vegan & plant-based diets
- Cardiovascular health
- Weight management
- Digestive health
- Sustainable & ethical considerations
- Anti-inflammatory diets
- Chronic disease management
- Convenience & product innovation
- Cultural or religious dietary restrictions
- Other, please explain:
- I would not recommend PBDAs

Q9. To whom would you recommend PBDAs? Choose all that apply.

- Infants/toddlers (≤ 3 y. o.)
- Children (4-12 y.o.)
- Adolescents (13-18 y.o.)
- Adults (19-64 y.o.)
- Older adults (≥ 65 y.o.)
- Those who already consume these products
- Those who have restricted diets (e.g. those with lactose intolerance, vegans, those who don't eat dairy)
- Those who are at high risk of cardiovascular disease (e.g., those with high cholesterol levels)
- Those who have osteoporosis
- Those who have overweight or obesity
- Other, please explain:
- Everyone
- I would not recommend PBDAs

Q10. Which types of PBDAs would you recommend?

- Only fortified PBDAs
- Only non-fortified PBDAs

- Any type, either fortified or non-fortified PBDAs
- I would not recommend PBDAs

Q11. Why do you NEVER recommend PBDAs to your patients/clients? Choose all that apply. [\[show only if they select None in Q7\]](#)

Q11 adapted. Why would you NOT recommend PBDAs to consumers? Choose all that apply. [\[show only if they select No in Q7 adapted\]](#)

- Because I think they are not necessary
- Because I think they are not “healthy food”
- Because of their taste & texture
- Because they are expensive
- Because they are intensively processed foods
- Because if not fortified, they have low nutritional value
- Because of cultural, religious, or ethical considerations
- Because I do not have enough information about them
- Other, please explain:

Perceptions / Attitudes

Q12. To what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements about PBDAs? [\[items presented in randomised order\]](#)

[response options: 1 = disagree, 2 = neither agree nor disagree, 3 = agree, 4 = I don't know]

PBDAs...

- can be part of a healthy diet
- are lactose-free
- are cholesterol-free
- are more processed than dairy products
- are more environmentally friendly than dairy products
- are less tasty than dairy products
- are more expensive than dairy products
- are not created equal; their nutritional profile depends on the plant source they are made of

Q13. Which statement do you agree the most with about PBDAs?

PBDAs...

- can *partly* substitute dairy products
- can *fully* substitute dairy products, regardless of whether they are fortified or not
- can *fully* substitute dairy products, only if they are fortified
- should be consumed in addition of dairy products, without substituting them

- cannot substitute dairy products

Q14. Which PBDAs do you think have a more favourable nutritional profile? [show only if they answer Agree in the last item of Q12]

- Those made of **legumes** (e.g., soy)
- Those made of **nuts** (e.g., almonds)
- Those made of **oats**
- Those made of **coconuts**
- Those made of **rice**
- Those made of **mixtures of the above ingredients**
- I don't know

Nutritional value compared to dairy products

Q15. Which of the following statements do you personally agree the most with?

- PBDAs are nutritionally **inferior** to dairy products
- PBDAs are nutritionally **equivalent** to dairy products
- PBDAs are nutritionally **equivalent** to dairy products only if they are **fortified**
- PBDAs are nutritionally **superior** to dairy products
- PBDAs are nutritionally **superior** to dairy products only if they are **fortified**
- I don't know

Q16. Please indicate whether you think PBDAs (non-fortified) have HIGHER, EQUAL, or LOWER content of each of the following nutrients compared to dairy products.

	Non-fortified PBDAs have HIGHER content than dairy products	Non-fortified PBDAs have EQUAL content to dairy products	Non-fortified PBDAs have LOWER content than dairy products	I don't know
Protein				
Fat				
Saturated fat				
Dietary cholesterol				
Carbohydrates				
Fiber				
Sugar				
Vitamin D				
Vitamin B12				
Vitamin B2 (riboflavin)				
Vitamin B9 (folate)				
Calcium				
Phosphorus				
Magnesium				
Iodine				

Potassium				
Zinc				
Calories				

Q17. What percentage of PBDAs in Spain [Portugal] do you think are fortified with vitamins and/or minerals? Drag the bar to indicate your answer or write the percentage directly in the box on the right.

Q18. Which vitamins and/or minerals do you think PBDAs in Spain [Portugal] are most frequently fortified with? Choose all that apply.

- Vitamin D
- Vitamin B12
- Vitamin B2 (riboflavin)
- Vitamin B9 (Folate)
- Calcium
- Phosphorus
- Magnesium
- Iodine
- Potassium
- Zinc
- Other, please specify:
- I don't know

Q19. Do you believe PBDAs should be fortified with vitamins and/or minerals?

- No
- Yes

Q20. Why do you think PBDAs should NOT be fortified? Choose all that apply. [show only if they select No in Q19]

- They are already nutritious
- They would be more processed
- It would not substantially change their nutrient bioavailability
- It would make the products more expensive
- Other, please explain:

Q21. Why do you think PBDAs should be fortified? Choose all that apply. [show only if they select Yes in Q19]

- To be more nutritious

- To be more easily promoted to consumers
- To be more equivalent to dairy products
- Other, please explain:

Inclusion of PBDAs in dietary guidelines

Q22. UK, Sweden, and USA are examples of countries that have incorporated fortified PBDAs in their national dietary guidelines (such as food pyramids). Do you believe PBDAs should be included also in the Spanish [Portuguese] dietary guidelines?

- No
- Yes
- Only if they are fortified with vitamins and/or minerals
- I don't know, I need more information

Q23. If fortified PBDAs were to be included in the Spanish [Portuguese] dietary guidelines, who do you think should be recommended to consume these products? Choose all that apply.

- Infants/toddlers (≤ 3 y. o.)
- Children (4-12 y.o.)
- Adolescents (13-18 y.o.)
- Adults (19-64 y.o.)
- Older adults (≥ 65 y.o.)
- Those who already consume these products
- People who have restricted diets (e.g., those with lactose intolerance, vegans, those who don't eat dairy)
- Those who are at high risk of cardiovascular disease (e.g., those with high cholesterol levels)
- Those who have osteoporosis
- People who have overweight or obesity
- I don't know
- Other, please explain:
- Everyone

Q24. If fortified PBDAs were to be included in the Spanish [Portuguese] dietary guidelines, with what frequency do you think these products should be recommended (assuming portion sizes are the same as with dairy products)?

- Lower** frequency than dairy products
- Same** frequency as dairy products
- Higher** frequency than dairy products
- I don't know

Q25. To improve your knowledge about PBDAs, what kind of information/training would you like to receive? Choose all that apply.

- Nutritional composition
- Health benefits & clinical evidence
- Fortification and bioavailability
- Processing and additives
- Sustainability and environmental impact
- Consumer trends and preferences
- Practical applications
- Other (please specify):

Demographics

Q26. Which gender do you identify with?

- Woman
- Man
- Other
- I prefer not to say

Q27. What is your age in years?

Q28. Do you have any dietary restrictions or preferences? Choose all that apply.

- Vegetarian
- Vegan
- Flexitarian
- Flexi-vegan
- Pescatarian
- Kosher
- Halal
- Dairy-free/ lactose-intolerant
- Gluten-free/ gluten-intolerant
- Food allergies or other intolerances
- Prefer not to say
- Other, please explain:
- I do not have any dietary restrictions or preferences

Q29. How often do you consume PBDAs yourself?

- Never
- Less than once a month
- 1-3 times per month

- 1-6 times per week
- 1 or more times per day

Q30. Which plant-based drink do you prefer the most?

- Soy drink
- Oat drink
- Almond drink
- Coconut drink
- I don't have a preference

Q31. Do you have any remaining comments?

Thank you for taking the time to fill in this survey. Your feedback is greatly appreciated.